

Research

Parking Spaces Optimisation: In-Depth Study of Mechanism Failure and Assessing Inter-Component Forces in Double-Stack Motor Controlled Parking System

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Abstract: The Double-Stack Motor Controlled Parking System, recognized for its compact and eco-friendly design, is gaining significant attention. This article focuses on the innovative Double-Stack Parking Mechanism known for optimizing space in residential areas. The renowned parking mechanism has the capability to park two vehicles at the same time. Key aspects investigated, including successful vehicle parking on platforms, Mechanism Failure, and inter-components forces, were investigated to enhance model development. SolidWorks simulation technique is crucial for analyzing forces between components and predicting mechanism failure under various vehicle loads. The study improves vehicle positioning accuracy and platform safety by utilizing force-sensitive resistor sensors, which activate corresponding light-emitting diodes (LEDs) upon vehicle contact. This renowned parking mechanism's ability to withstand different vehicle loads was evaluated, revealing a failure limit of 1600N or above. At 1600N vehicle load, the inter-component forces were analyzed, reflecting the simulation behavior in the parking mechanism. This research lays the foundation for multi-dimensional parking solutions, offering a promising approach to address residential parking space shortages.

Keywords: SolidWorks, Double-Stack, Parking System, Simulation, Inter-Component Force, Force Sensing Resistor

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Introduction

The reality of owning a car is that it often remains at rest during work hours or overnight, such as in residential areas. It can cause significant parking issues in cities or residential zones, requiring two separate parking spaces for each car

[1]. Residents of residential areas and urban cities can now benefit from a comprehensive scientific research study to improve their parking system. This research provides policymakers with a tool to facilitate life quality and reduce pollution by assessing a new angle on the parking problem [2]. The inability to park causes chaos in city planning; by expanding the number of off-street parking spots near or beside each building, we increase the distances between them, making parking convenient [3]. When it comes to the eternal pain of finding a parking spot, cruising is a factor, as drivers in many cities struggle to locate parking in core business districts and similarly busy spots during rush hours; those who can't find parking spots create parking problem for other people [4]. The volume of parking areas and the "economic cost" of using space for parking is high, and the cost of each parking spot determines the financial expense of providing parking. Thus, parking costs vary greatly based on the developer's location and parking facilities [5]. Private properties have garages and parking lots to solve the parking problem. Automated Multi-Level Vehicle Parking is the most famous off-street parking facility due to its multi-level car storage. This layout uses a motor or hydraulic parking automation technology to reduce car parking space [6].

Numerous technical studies have been written throughout the past few years. Researchers are doing their best to figure out how to optimize the Hydraulic vehicle parking mechanism, minimize stress failure, and automate it. This article [7] briefly covers automated parking and the author's efforts toward a model that can fit several cars in a compact space.

Mechanical and traditional parking aids are discussed in this article. This article's data can be used to generate a scaled-down functional model of a parking system that fits 6-24 automobiles in 32.17 with a 1/4-hp braking motor that will power the parking platform's sprocket and chain mechanism. This technical article examines how a scissor mechanism shifts a load before construction. Some factors such as durability, reliability, and strength should be considered, which will all affect the model's performance. Static analysis in Ansys Workbench evaluates stress, deformation, and stresses before deploying the scissor lift model [8]. Scissor lifts are used to lower and raise loads at defined heights. Because of its low cost, high reliability, and adaptability, the scissor lift has replaced many other lifting methods. Scissor lift models have an opening and closing leg sets to depict the mechanism's operation accurately. The model's leg sets, in particular, were analyzed for the deformation, stresses, and strains they create throughout the lifting process. Scientific research on weight optimization has been conducted to determine a feasible upper bound for loads that a scissor lift can handle. The structure is also experiencing fatigue during lifting objects, as discussed in the article [9]. This study provides an automated parking solution that chooses the best parking spot for the vehicle. Tower automatic parking can schedule, transport, implement, supervise, and collaborate. This parking includes the turntable, lift car frame, and parking system. Finite Element Analysis and experimental testing of critical parts verify their load safety. The driving unit hoists the load, the turntable mechanism rotates it, and the drive operation pushes and pulls it. [10]. This project reduces hypermarket and theatre parking lot traffic, which is expensive, by proposing a multi-level (4-layer) that shows parking control. Vertical 4-level parking controls exit and entry schedules. This mechanism has calculated hydraulic cylinder diameters and safety factor, Top Platform and fixed base frame analyzed through finite element analysis. The design's resilience meets all safety standards. Static design stresses are below the yield stress of the two main components (Top Platform and base frame), so mechanism is safe [11]. Parking mechanism must be designed to give output in the form of less manufacturing cost, efficient energy use, maintenance complexity must be less, and reduced safety risks. For this purpose, a side parking device has been proposed based on car driving force; motion and walking vehicle-shifting modules are two key parts of this side parking mechanism. Walking vehicle-shifting uses a side ward movable platform device to park cars laterally and prevent accidents. The components of this side parking mechanism comprise transmission and driving mechanism, cross cut mechanism that assists in car parking and averts car from skidding [12]. A lifting mechanism is needed to store vehicles automatically; thus, it provides storage capacity for more cars. This article elaborates development of lifting garages and the features of various 3D lifting garages. Mechanical analysis of the mechanism and the working principle has been discussed in the article. One drive for multi-plate assists

in garage lifting [13]. A rotational dual-layers compact mechanism is drafted to address the issue of parking in congested urban areas. The mechanism validity as a design concept is confirmed through ROBO PRO software. The device is primarily designed with a spinning dual-layer configuration, which involves the development of the frame, lifting and rotation. Given its compact design and great parking capacity, the proposed mechanism is an ideal solution to the persistent problem of inadequate parking spaces in residential neighborhoods [14]. With the economy growing, car usage rising, and public lands supplies scarce, traditional parking can potentially upgrade multi-level garages. This study proposes an intelligent modular cabinet parking mechanism for urban communities. The mechanism uses a 3×3 cabinet structure and could be handled via a cell phone remote connection [15]. A screw drive-based completely automatic 3D-book frame garage system has been proposed to solve parking issues, avoid chaos while parking, and evade complicated structures. The slide screws work with the transfer platforms to park and pick vehicles, improving the design and efficiency and making transportation easier. LabVIEW software is used to develop an interface for users; it has access to the garage and shows the current status of the garage [16]. A vertical garage carrier trolley has been developed to lessen the height of parking structures and the depth of underground garage excavations. An evaluation of the trolley's load distribution, foundation structural material steel and selection of the motor for the operation has been discussed in this article. This mechanism shows that a vertical garage is viable [17]. The three-dimensional garage may make good use of space and help residents park in residential neighborhoods, and this study proposes a vertical circulation parking device. The parking device mechanical system includes the primary structure, vehicle platform, and transmission mechanism. The parking mechanism has excellent market potential due to its space-minimizing benefits, straightforward design, and user-friendly operation [18]. Due to technology and green transportation programs, the number of bikes in communities has grown, resulting in a scarcity of bicycle parking and a disorderly bike arrangement. To overcome the concerns listed above, created a stereo garage for bicycles with an entrance and exiting garage, HCI, and control system [19].

In this scholarly article, we will focus on the central issues (Mechanism Failure, Vehicle Parking on the Platform, and Assessing Inter-Component Forces) in Double Stack Motor-Controlled Parking System, which is designed to alleviate the challenge of vehicle storage in congested metropolitan locations. This article also aimed to elaborate on the importance of inter-component forces between components in the mechanism, as previous research had yet to describe how these forces reflect the simulation of the mechanism. The area needed to park vehicles in the Double-Stack parking mechanism requires smaller space than conventional parking. Subsequently, prices to construct a house to park vehicles will be reduced. This parking mechanism illustrates how scientific information and engineering principles may be applied to help engineers and vehicle parking manufacturing firms discover a solution to a resident's parking issue in a residential neighborhood.

Solidworks Model

SOLIDWORKS CAD modeling application has been selected to model the Double-stacked motor-controlled parking system. SolidWorks application can also assist in the motion study of mechanical mechanisms. Besides their exceptional modeling ability, it is also centered on parametric methodology to optimize automatic mechanisms-based requirements.

Fig. 1: Double-Stack Motor Controlled Parking System SolidWorks Mode

Methods

Implementing a deductive research methodology in the simulation study enhances the reliability and preciseness of our findings. This approach enables us to consciously examine the behavior of the Double-Stack Parking mechanism in a real-world scenario, ensuring that our study is grounded on a well-established Finite Element Analysis approach.

2.1 Analysis of Mechanism Failure at various vehicle loads and Assessing Inter-components Forces between components through Inaugurate Various Boundary Conditions

The Double-Stack Motor Controlled Parking System consists of two platforms; the base platform is fixed, the Electric Linear Actuator will lower the top platform, and the vehicle will drive on it; this will give us a thorough understanding of the stress, strain, and deflection that occur while the mechanism is in operation, a static study analysis of the parking mechanism has been carried out in Solid Works. Before beginning the simulation, it is essential to be sure that there will be no interference between any of the mechanism’s components. Using the numerous Restraints available in SolidWorks, researchers and designers can ultimately constrain the mechanism before performing simulations. Within the framework of the provided planned mechanism, material was selected from the SolidWorks library and assigned to the model. During the assembly process, several distinct kinds of materials are commonly utilized, each chosen for the job based on the characteristics of its composition and its strength behavior. The Polylactic Acid (PLA) 3D-printing material has been selected from the SolidWorks material library to analyze the simulation study of the parking mechanism. PLA demonstrates a notable level of rigidity and stiffness, which can be advantageous for specific mechanical parts. However, this rigidity can also render it brittle, especially when subjected to high-stress circumstances or collisions.

Table 1. Mechanical and Thermal Properties of PLA

Mechanical and Thermal Properties	Value
Poisson’s Ratio	0.394
Yield strength [N. m-2]	5e+07
Thermal Conductivity [W/m.K]	0.2256

The fixture constraint in SolidWorks will assist the mechanism to fix the base because it should not move. The incorporation of contacts into the model will be the next step that we take. Although choosing contacts between different parts or components can sometimes be challenging, the components in the parking mechanism are in no-penetration and bonded contact condition, excluding contacts set between the actuator rod and the actuator body, which is set manually. A contact visualization plot helps observe the parts or components of the mechanism that are in contact with each other.

The blended curvature-based mesh was utilized to generate a mesh on the mechanism, while the mesh selection was employed for simulation. This choice was made due to the high-quality mesh provided by the Blended curvature-based mesh on the model's surface and its ability to supply mesh efficiently in certain portions of the model. To avoid mesh failure during simulation, it is necessary to apply mesh control on linear actuators and fillets on Linkage brackets. The meshing process was expedited, resulting in an adequately acceptable model for simulation.

Executing simulations in SolidWorks can be accomplished in two ways: by introducing design studies or by running individual simulations on the model. A separate simulation study on the model has been implemented to investigate the mechanism's stress, strain, and deflection due to the various vehicle loads acting at the model's top platform. On the model's top platform of the mechanism, we initially introduced a minimum vehicle load of 100N and a maximum vehicle load of 1900N. The following table presents the results of an individual simulation study performed on a model due to various vehicle loads.

The Mechanism is led by an Electric Linear Actuator that introduces a motion in the parking system. The Linear actuator's main components consist of the Rod and the actuator body. The Rod and Actuator body function can be considered as Flexible Subassemblies. It is well-established that both components have the proper end shapes, and both axis are aligned to produce the expected, intended motion (Up and Down). The maximum and lowest positions of the actuator Rod can be reached by inserting a limit mate between the upper and lower surface of the actuator body or by inserting a width mate into the shell with an accessible path. The placement of the actuator rod inside the actuator body and the selection of connections between components are the two most important considerations for accurate simulation. The most efficient method of determining the magnitude and direction of Resultant Forces between components in a model is to provide various contact (manual and component contact) conditions between all the components. Two studies have been introduced consisting of several boundary conditions incorporated into the simulation; the choice of meshing unquestionably affects the outcomes and findings of the model.

Table-2: Simulation Study of Double-Stack Motor Controlled Parking System at Various Vehicle Loads

Vehicle Load[N]	Yield Strength[N. m ⁻²]	Stress [N. m ⁻²]	Strain	Displacement [mm]	Mechanism Failure
100	5e+07	2.9e+06	1.167e-03	7.912e-01	Not Failed
200	5e+07	5.9e+06	2.233e-03	1.582e+00	Not Failed
300	5e+07	9.6e+06	3.649e-03	2.247e+00	Not Failed
400	5e+07	1.3e+07	4.612e-03	3.055e+00	Not Failed
500	5e+07	1.6e+07	5.765e-03	3.818e+00	Not Failed
600	5e+07	1.9e+07	7.297e-03	4.494e+00	Not Failed
700	5e+07	2.2e+07	8.514e-03	5.243e+00	Not Failed
800	5e+07	2.5e+07	9.750e-03	6.115e+00	Not Failed
900	5e+07	2.9e+07	1.09e-02	6.741e+00	Not Failed

1000	5e+07	3.1e+07	1.21e-02	7.644e+00	Not Failed
1100	5e+07	3.5e+07	1.33e-02	8.239e+00	Not Failed
1200	5e+07	3.8e+07	1.4e-02	9.1e+00	Not Failed
1300	5e+07	4.1e+07	1.5e-02	9.7e+00	Not Failed
1400	5e+07	4.5e+07	1.7e-02	1.0e+01	Not Failed
1500	5e+07	4.8e+07	1.8e-02	1.12e+01	Not Failed
1600	5e+07	5.1e+07	1.9e-02	1.19e+01	Failed
1700	5e+07	5.4e+07	2.0e-02	1.27e+01	Failed
1800	5e+07	5.8e+07	2.1e-02	1.34e+01	Failed
1900	5e+07	6.0e+07	2.3e-02	1.45e+01	Failed

2.1.1 Pins Distribution as Connectors instead Actual Pins in the Parking model during simulation

This case removes actual pins from the model and replaces them with pin connectors; the Rod and the actuator body are connected with pin connectors, when compared to static study that involves non-penetrating contact, the simulation requires a much less amount of time. Additionally, the pins on the rod and the Linear actuator bracket do not exhibit any translational or rotational behavior, both in the simulation and in the actual case. During simulation, a load of 1600N was applied on the top platform of the model; As a result, the entire structure will experience stress and deflection within the mechanism. The displacement in the model at 1600N is 1.4e+01 mm, strain 1.8e-02, and stress is 5.369e+07 which is more than the yield strength of the material shown in Figures (2-4).

There has also been evident hot stress and strains in the model, which will lead to failure in mechanism when we place this prototype into a real-world setting as stress in the mechanism exceeds the yield strength of the material.

Fig. 2: Stress due to Pins Distribution at 1600N

Fig.3: Strain due to Pins Distribution at 1600N

Fig. 4: Strain due to Pins Distribution at 1600N

2.1.2 Placement of 4 Links as a Connectors Instead of Actual Linear Actuators

The static simulation and the forces between the parking mechanism model components can also be analysed. This can be managed by disregarding Electric Linear Actuators and involving four connector links connected t

two pins (the Actuator rod pin and the actuator bracket pin) to acquire a vertex across both pins. As a consequence, the forces would be relocated. Implementing the split command tool in SolidWorks will enable it to configure links within the model; with the help of the two centres on the pins, this will be carried out effectively. Distributed Pins are deployed in the mechanism as an alternative to the actual pins employed in the simulation process. The displacement in the model at 1600N is $1.643e+01$ mm, strain is $7.304e-02$, and stress is $8.073e+08$, which is more than the yield strength of the material. As a result, the mechanism will fail, as shown in Figures (5-7).

Fig. 5: Stress due to Links at 1600N

Fig. 6: Strain due to Links at 1600N

Fig. 7: Displacement due to Links at 1600N

2.1 Track down presence of vehicle on Double-Stack Motor Controlled Parking System using Force Sensing Resistor (FSR) Sensor

Mechanical structures in various sectors rely on force-sensitive resistors. Robotic touch relies significantly on force-sensing resistor sensors, which record stiffness and help robots avoid obstructions during less-invasive incisions. Their ability to deftly navigate complex mechanical frameworks is on full display with this instrument [20]. Discussion in this article [21] centers on developing FSRs for several purposes, one of which is machine control, which could have implications for parking systems. This study's results [22] emphasize the vital role of force-sensing resistors in contact-control systems. Parking systems and other processes that require accurate force measurements could benefit from force-sensing resistor sensors. The purpose of this article is to present an in-depth discussion of FSR applications, including robotic grippers, that are conceptually comparable to the principles of parking systems. Force-sensing resistor sensors [23] exhibit a reduction in resistance when force is exerted on their active surface area or, in other words, the function of this sensor is based on the idea of resistance modulation in reaction to an applied force. This attribute renders them valuable for detecting vehicles on top and bottom platforms in double-stack parking systems due to the pressure exerted by the vehicle's wheel on the sensor's surface.

Fig.8: Force Sensing Resistor Sensors in Double-Stack Motor Controlled Parking System

Experimental

The hypothetical experimental setup focuses on the latest sort of parking mechanism that was modeled expressly for the purpose of storing two vehicles within a restricted amount of space to store them. The purpose of this experiment is to ensure that the car is successfully parked on both platforms for the user's safety.

The Double-Stack Motor Controlled Parking System accommodates the parking of two vehicles simultaneously. The bottom platform continues to remain in its original position. The next stage involves the motion of the top platform with the assistance of electric linear actuators. After a set period, the vehicle is lifted to a certain height above the base platform, and the procedure is repeated. 3D printing produces components that assemble the parking mechanism, including Linkages, Brackets (linkage and actuators), Pins, and Ramps (Top and Bottom).

Fig.9: Constructed Model of Double-Stack Motor Controlled Parking System

3.1 Accommodate Vehicle either on any Platform or on Both Platforms (Top and Bottom)

A popular and highly accurate sensor, the Force Sensing Resistor, is effectively integrated with the powerful microcontroller, the Arduino UNO. In state-of-the-art Double-Stack Parking systems, this complex combination is utilized to exactly ascertain if a vehicle is present on any of the two floors. An excellent combination of state-of-the-art technology and practical utility, this complex system is designed to maximize space usage and speed up the management of parking in urban areas.

Fig.10: Electronic Circuit Configuration of Force Sensing Resistor Sensors with Arduino UNO and Led
 The Arduino could read the Force Sensing Resistor (FSR) data by connecting it to a voltage divider circuit. To accomplish this, link the FSR's two ends to the breadboard's power supply and an analog input pin on the Arduino board. By connecting a 10kΩ resistor in parallel, a voltage divider is formed. In this setup, the Arduino can detect voltage changes produced by FSR sensor resistance changes.

A vehicle wheel pressing down on a Force-Sensitive Resistor (FSR) sensor lowers the sensor's electrical resistance; by making this adjustment, the microcontroller's input voltage and analog input signal will alter accordingly. The Arduino microcontroller can reliably detect the presence of a vehicle on any platform or both platforms by continuously monitoring these voltage values. The Arduino Nano microcontroller has been programmed with a modifiable threshold value to accurately differentiate between the exerted pressure on the sensor and its omission. When the measured voltage exceeds the predetermined threshold, the Arduino triggers the activation of an LED, signaling the vehicle detection on platforms either top or bottom.

Fig.11: Force Sensing Resistor Sensor Setup with Arduino UNO and Liquid Crystal on Breadboard

Fig.12. Setting Up Force Sensing Resistor Sensors Double-Stack Motor Controlled Parking System

Results and Discussion

When it comes to predicting how mechanisms will react in real-world situations, including a wide range of physical impacts such as vehicle loads on Double-stack parking system, Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is an indispensable computational tool. This convoluted approach is fundamental to engineering and is applied widely for the thoughtful designing of mechanical mechanism.

Fig.13: Stress due to various Vehicle Loads on Double-Stack Motor Controlled Parking System

Employing Finite Element Analysis (FEA) in a double-stack parking system evaluation allowed researchers to determine how well it could withstand different vehicle loads. According to static failure theory, instability occurs when a structure's peak stress is higher than its yield strength. The simulation results reflect that there was no likelihood of failure because the mechanism's maximum stress levels were below the yield limit across vehicle loads from 100N to 1500N, Although the mechanism would collapse as stresses higher than the yield limit at 1600N and further on since such material can't withstand such high amounts of stress. The provided graphs depict the results of this static study.

Fig. 14: Strain due to various Vehicle Loads on Double-Stack Motor Controlled Parking System

Fig. 15: Displacement due to various Vehicle Loads on Double-Stack Motor Controlled Parking System

The stress and displacement in the parking mechanism exceed with increasing vehicle loads, as evidenced by the graphs from the static investigation. An in-depth understanding of the forces operating between the components of a mechanical mechanism is crucial for accurately simulating its static behavior in a simulation environment. These intra-component forces can be accurately computed in the model with the help of unique algorithms and simulation software. Two distinct scenarios with distinctive boundary conditions have been deliberately developed to explore the component forces in the double-stack Motor controlled parking mechanism. These scenarios, which involve simulation under various boundary states, enable it to observe and quantify the forces that interact with the constituent components.

Fig. 16: Intra Component forces due to Pins distribution at 1600N in Double-Stack Motor Controlled Parking System

Fig. 17: Intra Component forces due to Links at 1600N in Double-Stack Motor Controlled Parking System

Table -3: Resultant Forces between components in Double -Stack Motor Controlled Parking System

Scenario	Vehicle Load [N]	Front Link FRes [N]	Rear Link FRes [N]	Top Link Front Brackets FRes [N]	Top Link Rear Brackets FRes [N]
Pins	1600	1505	243	1082	336
Link	1600	1648	634	1082	347

The findings from these studies suggest that the front linkage in a parking system is subjected to a more significant number of resultant forces than the rear linkage. Furthermore, the front brackets, particularly those attached to the top platform, are subjected to stresses more effective than those experienced by their rear brackets. In the link scenario, the actuators, which are essential components for movement in double-stack parking systems, are replaced by links, which, as a result, the mechanism experiences significantly higher stress rather than stress due to pins distribution. The stress distribution within the mechanism is drastically altered due to this substitution, which is the cause of the observed inequalities in the front and rear links and brackets.

Conclusion

In conclusion, The suggested Double-Stack Motor Controlled parking mechanism has been designed to resolve the issue of immobilized traffic, such as in an office or residential area. The family can park two vehicles using the single parking mechanism without any inconvenience, which is ideal for their needs.

1. This parking system is more efficient than traditional parking and takes less space. Another advantage of this mechanism is that it is very safe for pedestrians and reduces the possibility of accidents.
2. The stress distribution introduced by the vehicle loads was investigated through Finite Element Analysis in SolidWorks.
3. The mechanism's failure has been investigated due to excessive vehicle loads.
4. Fillets should be used in place of sharp edges to prevent meshing failure during simulation to guarantee a dense mesh in these places.
5. Forces between components in the mechanism provide a clear image of the stress locations and magnitudes that correlate to the outcomes of simulations based on reality.
6. The precision and reliability of the procedure of locating automobiles on any platform will be determined depending on the quality of the FSR and the adjustment of threshold value in the Arduino's programming.
7. There is a clearance between the top platform's surface and the vehicle's top surface; whenever we need to park or unpark a car from the top platform, we do not need to move the vehicle from the bottom platform.

The Electric linear actuators noticed an increase in applied force when the mechanism was lifted, indicating the crucial role of the linear actuators in the parking function. The results of the simulated motion study demonstrate the feasibility of implementing a Double-Stack parking mechanism in real-world locations, such as residential districts with limited space.

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